

Intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade globally

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Intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade represent an indicator that measures the proportion of a country's spending on intellectual property in relation to its overall trade. This parameter reflects how much an economy spends on acquiring rights to use patents, trademarks, copyrights, and other forms of intellectual property from foreign entities. In a global knowledge-based economy, companies frequently purchase technology, know-how, and innovations protected by intellectual property from other countries to remain competitive and develop their own products and services. The share of these payments in total trade can indicate the level of a country's reliance on foreign technologies or innovations. A high percentage of intellectual property payments relative to total trade can signal that a country makes extensive use of foreign-developed technologies, investing in licenses to access patents and technologies not produced domestically. This does not necessarily indicate a weakness but can highlight robust technological exchange and active participation in global innovation. Conversely, a lower value may indicate that a country develops its own technologies internally or is less involved in international intellectual property agreements. This indicator is crucial for understanding global knowledge and technology flows and how these dynamics influence a country's competitive positioning in the global economy. It also provides insight into how integrated a country is in the global knowledge and innovation markets. Data available pertains to the period between 2016 and 2022.

Intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade globally in 2022. The data on intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade provides an interesting overview of how countries differ in investing and paying for the use of intellectual property rights, such as patents, trademarks, copyrights, and know-how. These payments represent a significant share of international trade for many countries, particularly advanced economies, where technological know-how and intellectual rights are fundamental drivers of economic growth and competitiveness. In 2022, countries such as Switzerland, Ireland, Malta, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg dominate the rankings, with intellectual property payment percentages reaching 100% of total trade or close to it. These countries are known for being financial and technological hubs where the protection and exploitation of intellectual property play a crucial role in the economic model. Intellectual property spending in these cases reflects a strong exchange of intellectual rights, due to the presence of multinational companies, research centers, and high-tech industries operating globally. These countries often host the legal headquarters of large multinationals that manage and centralize their intellectual property activities, contributing to the particularly high level of spending on these intangible assets. Costa Rica, with a percentage of 75.3%, highlights the significant role that intellectual property payments play in the trade of an emerging country. This result can be seen as indicative of successful policies aimed at

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integrating the country into global value chains in sectors that require the use of foreign technologies and patents, such as the information and communication technology industry. In Japan (71.9%) and Singapore (71.1%), the high percentage reflects these economies' strong dependence on advanced technologies and foreign know-how. Despite being leading nations in technological development, their economies are highly integrated into global intellectual property flows. This demonstrates that even highly developed economies, with vast internal innovation capacities, can rely on external technologies to sustain their growth. Countries such as Argentina (57.2%), Canada (57%), and Chile (51.6%) rank lower than European countries but still maintain high percentages. In the case of Argentina, for example, such a high percentage could suggest significant reliance on the purchase of intellectual property rights to support industrial and technological development. The need to access foreign technology to boost sectors such as energy, telecommunications, and industrial production is evident in these emerging economies. Brazil (45.9%) and the United Kingdom (45.5%) show elevated spending levels compared to other developed and developing economies, emphasizing the important role that foreign know-how plays in their economy. The United Kingdom, despite being known for its strong innovation capacity, continues to invest significantly in acquiring intellectual property from abroad, particularly in the technology and science sectors. The United States (38.9%) and South Korea (39%), two of the most technologically advanced economies in the world, show relatively moderate percentages, suggesting that while they are strong producers of innovation, they also make substantial use of foreign technologies. South Korea, for instance, is a giant in the production of electronic and technological goods but must also incur significant payments for the use of technologies developed abroad, particularly in the field of semiconductor and software production. Among emerging economies, India (34.1%) and China (35.1%) show increasing participation in global intellectual property trade. Despite China's growing ability to generate domestic innovation, it continues to make extensive use of foreign technology. This can be seen as part of its economic development strategy, which has favored integration into global supply chains. On the other hand, India is emerging as a technological and industrial hub, and its intellectual property spending reflects a significant investment in foreign technologies to support its rapid economic development. In the case of Italy (19.9%), the lower level of spending compared to other advanced economies may indicate greater self-sufficiency in developing internal intellectual property or a lesser degree of participation in the global trade of intellectual rights compared to countries like France (37.3%) or Germany (23.6%). This could be linked to the country's economic structure, with a prevalence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and a lesser presence of large multinationals compared to other European countries. Looking at the lower percentages in the ranking, countries such as Mexico (1.7%), Bangladesh (2.5%), and Nigeria (9.1%) show very low intellectual property spending. This may reflect limited participation in knowledge and innovation markets due to lesser integration into global value chains and reduced use of advanced technologies. In these countries, local industries may be more focused on traditional or low-tech sectors, and consequently, the demand for intellectual property rights from abroad is reduced. At the bottom of the ranking, we find countries such as Armenia, Azerbaijan, Benin, Bahrain, Kuwait, Nepal, Oman, Qatar, and Saudi Arabia, which in 2022 reported zero spending on intellectual property as a percentage of total trade. This figure could indicate that these economies have little need to purchase intellectual property rights from abroad or that they operate primarily in economic sectors that do not require advanced technology. In some cases, this could also reflect a lack of infrastructure or insufficient policies to encourage the adoption of foreign technologies and innovation. In conclusion, the data on intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade provides a snapshot of the degree to which economies are integrated into global innovation and knowledge markets. More developed economies tend to invest heavily in intellectual property, both internally and through the acquisition of foreign rights, while emerging and less developed economies show limited integration, often due to a lesser need for

advanced technology or reduced innovation capacities. This indicator is useful for understanding the strategic role of intellectual property in strengthening economic competitiveness and innovation on a global scale.

Intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade globally between 2016 and 2022. The data on intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade between 2016 and 2022 reveals significant trends of both growth and decline across different countries. Intellectual property payments are a key indicator of a country's economic integration into global innovation flows, and the variations observed during this period reflect changes in economic policies, trade dynamics, and the adoption of external technologies. A remarkable case is Yemen, which recorded an impressive increase in intellectual property payments, rising from 1.2% in 2016 to 38.1% in 2022, with an absolute variation of 36.9 percentage points and a 3075% increase. This growth can be attributed to increased demand for foreign technologies or a shift in the economy, where imports of high-tech goods have become essential to trade. However, Yemen's complex political and socio-economic context may have contributed to this increase, with an economy increasingly dependent on goods and services from abroad. Zambia and Botswana also saw substantial growth, with increases of 1120% and 951.35%, respectively. These countries, traditionally tied to more conventional economic sectors, appear to have increased their reliance on foreign technologies, likely to modernize their industries and support economic growth. The rise in intellectual property spending in these countries may reflect a shift in economic structure, with greater emphasis on imported technologies to drive industrialization and innovation. Costa Rica, with a 512.20% increase, represents an interesting example of an emerging economy that has adopted a development strategy based on integration into global intellectual property flows. The 63 percentage point growth can be seen as a sign of success in positioning itself as a center for technology and knowledge-based services, attracting foreign investment, and improving its international competitiveness. Among the countries that showed more moderate growth, Sweden and the United Kingdom stand out, with increases of 54.51% and 51.16%, respectively. Both of these countries are known for being global innovation leaders, and the rise in intellectual property spending may reflect greater integration into global value chains and increased use of foreign technologies to maintain a competitive edge. In Germany, intellectual property spending grew by 66.20%, with an increase of 9.4 percentage points. This could be indicative of the continued reliance of the German economy on foreign technologies, despite the country being a leader in technological innovation. The manufacturing sector, in particular, makes extensive use of advanced imported technologies, which could explain this trend. On the opposite front, several countries experienced significant decreases in intellectual property payments. Mozambique saw a sharp decline, falling from 8.3% in 2016 to 0.3% in 2022, a reduction of 96.39%. This decline could indicate a decrease in imports of advanced technologies or reduced integration of the local economy into global intellectual property flows. Factors such as economic instability and a lack of innovation incentive policies may have contributed to this drop. Mexico, with an 86.72% decrease, represents another significant case. The reduction in intellectual property payments could be linked to lower demand for foreign technologies or a greater emphasis on domestic production and local innovation, reducing reliance on imported patents and technologies. Another notable decline is seen in Singapore, which recorded a 28.9% reduction, dropping from 100% in 2016 to 71.1% in 2022. This decline may reflect a more targeted strategy toward domestic technology development or reduced reliance on global intellectual property flows. However, despite the decline, Singapore remains a global technology hub, implying that the country continues to be highly integrated into intellectual property trade. Finland also saw a significant drop of 53.03%, with a reduction in intellectual property

spending possibly attributed to decreased need for external technology, favoring more internal development. However, this decline may also indicate reduced integration into global technology markets. Among European countries, Italy recorded a 21.96% decrease, falling from 25.5% in 2016 to 19.9% in 2022. This decline may be linked to the country's economic structure, characterized by a strong presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which may make less use of advanced external technologies compared to other larger European economies. However, the reduction could also reflect an improvement in the internal innovation capacity of Italian companies, reducing the need to rely on foreign technologies. The United States, another global leader in innovation, saw an 18.11% reduction in intellectual property payments. While the U.S. remains one of the main players in the knowledge economy, this decrease could be indicative of greater technological self-sufficiency or less need to acquire foreign technology to support economic growth. However, the relatively high level of spending in 2022 (38.9%) shows that the U.S. continues to rely heavily on global intellectual property flows. Argentina experienced a 17.22% decrease, which could be related to the internal economic challenges the country has faced in recent years. The reduction in intellectual property payments may reflect a drop in investment in foreign technologies or a restructuring of the economy towards sectors less dependent on advanced technologies. Finally, it is interesting to observe the performance of some developing countries like Senegal and Ethiopia, which saw moderate increases in intellectual property payments, up 416.67% and 171.43%, respectively. Although the absolute percentages remain low, these increases indicate growing interest in adopting foreign technologies as a tool for promoting economic growth and innovation. In conclusion, the data on intellectual property payments between 2016 and 2022 reveal deep disparities between countries, with some significantly increasing their integration into global innovation flows, while others have reduced their reliance on foreign technologies. These variations are influenced by a combination of economic, political, and technological factors that determine the extent to which countries participate in global intellectual property trade. More developed economies tend to be more integrated into knowledge markets, but many emerging economies are also making significant progress in this area, while some developing economies continue to struggle to integrate into global technology and innovation flows.

Economic policies. Economic policies aimed at promoting intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade must be designed with a specific focus on improving a country's capacity to create, protect, and exploit intellectual property. In a global knowledge-based economy, the role of intellectual property (IP) is crucial for driving innovation, stimulating economic growth, and enhancing international competitiveness. A country's ability to attract and retain investment depends largely on the level of protection and valorization of intellectual property. Therefore, policies must be aimed at promoting the creation of a favorable environment for innovation and the growth of intellectual property-related trade. One of the fundamental priorities to increase intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade is investment in research and development (R&D). Public and private support for advanced research projects must be a key component of the economic strategy. Governments can adopt fiscal policies that offer incentives for R&D investments, such as tax credits, tax relief, and grants for companies investing in innovative and patentable technologies. These incentives encourage companies to invest in creating new intellectual property and improve their ability to compete in international markets. Furthermore, promoting partnerships between universities, research centers, and the private sector is essential to facilitate the transfer of technologies and knowledge from academia to business, accelerating the commercialization of innovations. Another crucial element is improving the regulatory and legal framework for intellectual

property protection. Companies are more likely to invest in creating and exploiting intellectual property in an environment where property rights are clearly defined and adequately protected. A solid regulatory framework that ensures stringent protection of patents, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets incentivizes investment in technology and innovation. Countries that develop and maintain effective intellectual property protection systems can attract global businesses that see these economies as favorable contexts for innovation. Combating counterfeiting and piracy must also be a priority, as these practices erode the value of intellectual property and discourage investment in advanced technologies. Technological and digital infrastructure represents another fundamental pillar in promoting intellectual property payments. The adoption of advanced digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, the internet of things (IoT), and blockchain, facilitates the creation of new products and services that can be protected by intellectual property rights. Furthermore, the development of high-speed telecommunications networks, such as 5G networks, enables companies to collaborate in real-time and on a global scale, fostering innovation and the growth of digital trade. Government policies must therefore focus on developing modern technological infrastructure that supports innovation. In particular, it is essential to provide small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with access to advanced technologies and digital platforms that allow them to participate in the international trade of intellectual property. This approach helps to reduce the technology gap and integrate SMEs into global value chains. Another key component for promoting intellectual property payments in total trade is education and training. Knowledge-based economies require a highly skilled workforce capable of developing, managing, and protecting intellectual property rights. Governments must invest in advanced training programs in fields such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) while also promoting legal and business training for intellectual property experts. Integrating education in innovation and intellectual property into school and university curricula is essential to create a new generation of innovators and entrepreneurs capable of competing internationally. Additionally, it is crucial for businesses and professionals to be aware of the economic benefits of protecting and strategically using intellectual property rights, fostering a culture of innovation that permeates all economic sectors. International trade policies must play a central role in promoting intellectual property payments. Countries need to negotiate trade agreements that include clauses on intellectual property protection and compliance, ensuring that domestic businesses can operate in a safe environment when exporting their innovative products and services. The creation of global networks for intellectual property trade facilitates access to foreign markets, reducing barriers and enabling companies to monetize their intellectual property rights on a global scale. Governments must actively support their businesses in navigating complex international regulatory systems and negotiating bilateral and multilateral treaties that encourage the exchange of protected technologies and innovations through patents and trademarks. Another important tool for promoting intellectual property in global trade is support for the internationalization of businesses, particularly SMEs. Small and medium-sized enterprises often lack the resources needed to protect their intellectual property rights in international markets. Governments can offer financial incentives and support for registering patents and trademarks abroad, as well as advice on managing and protecting intellectual property rights internationally. Additionally, programs can be implemented to facilitate SMEs' access to foreign markets and allow them to capitalize on the opportunities offered by global intellectual property rights trade. Regional innovation policies can play a key role in promoting intellectual property growth. Governments can create innovation ecosystems, such as technology parks and industrial districts, that encourage collaboration between businesses, universities, and research institutes. These hubs can facilitate technology transfer and the trade of intellectual property rights, creating a fertile environment for the creation of new patents, trademarks, and copyrights. Regions that develop targeted policies to incentivize intellectual property can attract foreign investment and become global centers of innovation. Finally, international cooperation is

essential to promoting intellectual property trade. Governments must collaborate to harmonize intellectual property protection systems, making it easier and safer for businesses to register and protect their rights in different countries. Active participation in international organizations regulating intellectual property, such as the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), is essential to ensure that national policies align with global standards and facilitate cross-border trade in intellectual property rights. In conclusion, to promote intellectual property payments as a percentage of total trade, governments must adopt a multi-dimensional approach that includes incentives for research and development, a robust regulatory framework, the development of technological infrastructure, education and training, favorable international trade policies, and support for the internationalization of businesses. Only through concerted efforts in these areas can global economies increase their participation in intellectual property flows, promoting innovation, competitiveness, and economic growth on a global scale.

Conclusions. The average value of intellectual property payments as a percentage of international trade grew between 2016 and 2022 from 22.33 to 23.46, an increase of 5.04%. This figure means that more than 20% of international trade involves intellectual property. Some countries experienced significant growth in intellectual property payments as a percentage of international trade, far exceeding the average, including Yemen (+3075.00% between 2016 and 2022), Zambia (+1200%), Botswana (+951.35%), Costa Rica (+512.20%), and Senegal (+416.67%). On the other hand, several countries saw a decrease in this value during the period considered, including Togo (-67.74%), Namibia (-77.14%), Mexico (-86.72%), Rwanda (-93.33%), and Mozambique (-96.39%).

Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Switzerland	100	Romania	22	Dominican Republic	5,2
Ireland	100	Portugal	21,9	Zimbabwe	5,1
Malta	100	Ukraine	21,2	Uganda	4,8
Netherlands	100	Jamaica	20,9	Montenegro	4,7
Luxembourg	98,8	Indonesia	20,8	Lithuania	4,4
Costa Rica	75,3	Denmark	20,5	Panama	4
Sweden	72	Belgium	20,4	Iran, Islamic Rep.	3,8
Japan	71,9	Czechia	20,3	Jordan	3,6
Singapore	71,1	Israel	20,3	Paraguay	3,6
Argentina	57,2	Italy	19,9	Kyrgyz Republic	3,4
Canada	57	Austria	19,1	Bosnia and Herzegovina	3,2
Chile	51,6	United Arab Emirates	18,1	Senegal	3,1
North Macedonia	51,2	Slovak Republic	18	Cambodia	2,9
Brazil	45,9	Philippines	17,6	Bangladesh	2,5
United Kingdom	45,5	Peru	16,7	Tunisia	2,1
Thailand	43,5	Ghana	15,8	Ethiopia	1,9
Russian Federation	41,7	Albania	15,7	Mexico	1,7
New Zealand	40	Angola	15,5	Cote d'Ivoire	1,5
South Africa	39,9	Ecuador	15,2	Mauritania	1,4
Korea, Rep.	39	Slovenia	15,1	Tanzania	1,3
Botswana	38,9	Bulgaria	14,2	Togo	1
United States	38,9	Moldova	13,8	Cameroon	0,9
Yemen, Rep.	38,1	Trinidad and Tobago	12,7	Guinea	0,8

France	37,3	Norway	12,1	Namibia	0,8
China	35,1	Egypt, Arab Rep.	11,9	Nicaragua	0,5
Guatemala	34,4	Belarus	11,6	Burundi	0,3
India	34,1	Georgia	11,6	Burkina Faso	0,3
Spain	34	Greece	10,9	Iraq	0,3
Cyprus	32,6	Pakistan	10,6	Mozambique	0,3
Colombia	29,9	Uzbekistan	10,4	Rwanda	0,1
Australia	28,4	Madagascar	9,3	Armenia	0
Poland	28,3	Nigeria	9,1	Azerbaijan	0
Hungary	27,9	Algeria	8,7	Benin	0
Serbia	27,5	Morocco	8,3	Bahrain	0
Croatia	26,6	Hong Kong SAR, China	7,3	Kuwait	0
Finland	25,6	Myanmar	7,1	Lao PDR	0
Kenya	25,3	Kazakhstan	6,9	Sri Lanka	0
Malaysia	24,9	Estonia	6,8	Mali	0
Iceland	24,7	Mongolia	6,7	Niger	0
El Salvador	24,6	Mauritius	6,2	Nepal	0
Germany	23,6	Brunei Darussalam	6,1	Oman	0
Uruguay	23,4	Zambia	6,1	Qatar	0
Honduras	23,3	Latvia	5,7	Saudi Arabia	0
Turkiye	22,2	Vietnam	5,7	Tajikistan	0

Reference

Arnone, M.; Leogrande, A. (2024). The Green Trilemma: Energy Efficiency, Banking Stability and Climate Risk in the ESG Context at World Level.

Arnone, M.; Leogrande, A. (2024). The People You Can Count on in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4873511.

Arnone, M.; Leogrande, A. (2024). The Sustainability of the Factoring Chain in Europe in the Light of the Integration of ESG Factors. Available at SSRN 4880150.

Arnone, M., Angelillis, B., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Graduates, Training and Employment Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4850961.

Arnone, M., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Access to Credit in the Context of the ESG Framework at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4912994.

Arnone, M., Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2024). Banking Stability in the ESG Framework Across Italian Regions (No. 121452). University Library of Munich, Germany.

- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. Available at SSRN.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4782193.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771132.
- Leogrande, A., Resta, E., & Costantiello, A. (2024). The Renunciation of Healthcare Services in the Italian Regions in the ESG Context. Available at SSRN 4746676.
- Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Air Pollution in the ESG Model at the World Level. In *Intersecting Environmental Social Governance and AI for Business Sustainability* (pp. 93-122). IGI Global.
- Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-22.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-13.
- Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.
- Resta, E., Logroscino, G., Tafuri, S., Peter, P., Noviello, C., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Mental Health Index across the Italian Regions in the ESG Context (No. 3cztm). Center for Open Science.
- Resta, E., Resta, O., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The hospital emigration to another region in the light of the environmental, social and governance model in Italy during the period 2004-2021. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1880.

Salvatore, D., Magazzino, C., Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2024). The economic determinants of world disorder events: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 46(4), 740-756.